

Drivers' Willingness to Recapitalize Informal Minibus Fleets: Evidence from Ghana's Trotro Sector

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Abstract

The dominance of informal minibus transport services, popularly known as trotros, remains central to urban mobility in Ghana despite longstanding concerns over aging fleets, safety risks, and weak regulation. This study investigates the willingness of trotro drivers to participate in fleet downsizing, recapitalization, and modernization reforms within the Kumasi Metropolitan Area. Using a quantitative cross-sectional design, 397 valid responses were collected across seven major terminals. Data were analyzed through descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and logistic regression to examine relationships between socioeconomic factors and drivers' reform readiness. The findings reveal widespread awareness of modernization initiatives (95%) and strong willingness to recapitalize when provided with financial support (79%), access to low-interest loans (65%), or cooperative ownership models (61%). However, high vehicle costs, lack of collateral, and limited trust in financial institutions emerged as key barriers. Drivers emphasized the importance of job security (80%) and practical training to enable smooth transition to new vehicle technologies. Notably, 78.8% expressed strong willingness to adopt electric minibuses, though concerns about initial cost, charging infrastructure, and battery lifespan persist. Statistical analysis confirmed that income level significantly influences willingness to recapitalize ($\chi^2 = 92.94, p < 0.001$), with lower- and middle-income drivers demonstrating higher reform enthusiasm. The study concludes that successful recapitalization and e-mobility transitions depend on integrated financial schemes, targeted driver education, and stakeholder collaboration that safeguard livelihoods while advancing transport modernization.

Keywords: Recapitalization, Trotro, Informal Transport, Electric Buses, Drivers' Willingness, Ghana, Fleet Reform

1. Introduction

Public transport systems in many developing countries are dominated by informal minibus services that emerged as substitutes for weak or collapsing state-led bus networks. In Ghana, the trotro industry has become the backbone of urban mobility, accounting for nearly 86% of road-based public transport trips in Accra (Kumar & Barrett, 2008). These vehicles—mostly Nissan Urvans and Toyota Hiace minibuses—provide affordable and flexible services for millions of commuters each day.

However, the sector is characterized by an aging fleet, poor safety standards, and limited regulatory oversight. Vehicles are often decades old, poorly maintained, and prone to breakdowns. Operators face harsh economic realities, including high fuel costs, oversaturation of the market, and the absence of social protection (Agyei-Mensah, 2017). At the same time, drivers rely heavily on unions such as the Ghana Private Road Transport Union (GPRTU), which regulate access to terminals but offer little incentive for modernization.

In response, policy discussions in Ghana increasingly emphasize recapitalization—the replacement of aging trotros with modern, efficient vehicles, including electric minibuses. Such reforms aim to improve

safety, reduce emissions, and create a more reliable public transport system. Yet the success of these initiatives depends critically on drivers' willingness to embrace change, since their acceptance or resistance ultimately determines whether reforms can be implemented at scale.

Despite the urgent need for fleet renewal, recapitalization faces significant resistance from trotro drivers and operators. Many are hesitant to invest in new vehicles due to financial vulnerability, lack of access to affordable credit, and fears of job loss if reforms include downsizing. Previous attempts at formalization, such as Metro Mass Transit and pilot Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) schemes, struggled in part because of active opposition from private operators who viewed reforms as threats to their livelihoods (Agyemang, 2015; Venter, 2012).

This study examines the willingness of trotro drivers in Ghana to embrace reform and fleet recapitalization, with a particular focus on downsizing and the adoption of modern vehicle technologies. By focusing on drivers' perspectives, this study fills a critical gap in transport policy discourse. Whereas commuters, unions, and policymakers are often foregrounded in discussions of reform, the individual willingness of drivers remains underexplored. Insights from this research will inform the design of recapitalization policies that balance driver livelihoods with public interest, contribute to debates on how to align informal transport with Ghana's e-mobility and sustainability agenda, and provide evidence for regulators and unions on incentive structures most likely to secure driver buy-in.

2. Literature Review

The evolution of Ghana's public transport sector has been shaped by repeated attempts at state-led interventions and the simultaneous dominance of informal operators. Post-independence governments experimented with formal bus services such as the Omnibus Services Authority (OSA), State Transport Company (STC), and City Express Services (CES). However, inefficiency, poor maintenance, and heavy reliance on subsidies led to their eventual collapse or privatization in the 1990s (Nyarku, Kusi & Agyemang, 2017).

The vacuum created by the decline of formal systems coincided with worsening economic crises of the 1970s and 1980s. Hyperinflation, fuel shortages, and state withdrawal from mass transit provision fostered the rise of privately owned minibuses, popularly known as trotros. These vehicles became the de facto urban transport system, operating with little regulation or fleet management (Mantey et al., 2021). This legacy has created a system where drivers operate under informal norms, influencing their perceptions of modernization, recapitalization, and reform.

To coordinate operations and resist excessive state oversight, unions such as the Ghana Private Road Transport Union (GPRTU), the Ghana Co-operative Transport Association (GCTA), the Progressive Transport Owners Association (PROTOA), and the Ghana National Transport Owners Association (GNTOA) emerged. These unions collect fees, regulate access to terminals, and mediate disputes (Fouracre, Kwakye, Okyere & Silcock, 1994). While they offer drivers a collective voice, unions also serve as gatekeepers. Their control over routes and terminals creates a dual reality: drivers gain protection but also face rigid fee structures and limited autonomy. Since unions often prioritize financial sustainability over modernization, they can act as both enablers and barriers to recapitalization.

Most trotro drivers operate under precarious financial conditions. Studies indicate that drivers often lack pensions, healthcare, and job security, forcing them into long working hours with limited savings capacity (Agyei-Mensah, 2017). Their ability to invest in new vehicles is further undermined by barriers to credit. Commercial banks are reluctant to provide loans due to collateral requirements, high interest rates, and legal ambiguities around vehicle ownership that prevent repossession in cases of default (Raman & Halm, 1990). This context of financial insecurity explains why many drivers perceive

recapitalization as risky. For them, replacing old vehicles may imply uncertain returns, increased debt, and heightened exposure to market volatility.

Experiences from other countries provide valuable insights into drivers' attitudes toward reform. In South Africa, the taxi recapitalization programme initially aimed to replace aging minibuses with safer vehicles. While approximately 44,000 vehicles were scrapped by 2011, the programme fell short of expectations due to weak enforcement and drivers' fears of job losses and fare increases (RSA, 2012; Boudreaux, 2006). Moreover, failure to adequately involve unions in Johannesburg's BRT rollout led to violent resistance, underscoring the need for stakeholder engagement (Venter, 2012). Conversely, examples from Cape Town show that when minibus taxis were integrated as feeders into formal networks, resistance declined, and operators accepted reforms as complementary rather than threatening (Behrens et al., 2015). More recent behavioural studies emphasize that incentive framing plays a crucial role: drivers respond more positively to “reward-based” reforms (e.g., subsidies, scrappage bonuses) than to penalty-driven approaches (Plano & Behrens, 2022).

3. Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative cross-sectional survey design, which is suitable for capturing the demographic characteristics, operational practices, and reform preferences of trotro drivers at a single point in time. The design allowed for the analysis of relationships between socio-economic factors and drivers' willingness to recapitalize or adopt new vehicle technologies.

The research was conducted in Kumasi, Ghana, focusing on drivers operating at major trotro terminals including Santasi, Kotei, Tech Junction, Kotwi, Kejetia, Anloga Junction, and Adum. These stations were purposively selected because they represent high-demand routes and accommodate a diverse range of operators. The study population comprised active drivers, irrespective of vehicle ownership arrangements (owned, rented, or hire purchase).

A total of 450 questionnaires were distributed across the selected trotro stations. Out of these, 397 valid responses were obtained and analyzed, representing an effective response rate of 88.2%. The minimum required sample size was determined using Cochran's formula for an unknown population size: $n_0 = Z^2p(1-p)/e^2$, where $Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence level), $p = 0.5$ (maximum variability), and $e = 0.05$ (margin of error). This yielded a minimum sample size of 385 respondents. The actual sample of 397 exceeded this threshold, ensuring statistical precision and representativeness.

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire consisting of five sections: (i) demographic information, (ii) operational profile, (iii) awareness and willingness to recapitalize, (iv) barriers to financing and operational challenges, and (v) perceptions of electric minibuses. The questions were predominantly closed-ended, using categorical and Likert-scale formats to facilitate quantitative analysis. The researcher personally administered paper questionnaires at the selected terminals. Completed responses were checked for consistency and transferred into KoboCollect for digital storage. Where necessary, respondents with limited literacy were assisted through oral administration. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was secured before completion.

Data were exported from KoboCollect into Microsoft Excel for initial cleaning and descriptive summaries. Further statistical processing and predictive modeling were conducted in RapidMiner, which provided tools for cross-tabulation, chi-square testing, and regression analysis. The analytical process comprised three stages: (1) Descriptive Statistics—frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were generated to summarize respondents' demographic and operational profiles; (2) Cross-tabulations and Chi-square Tests—bivariate analyses were performed to examine associations between variables such as age, education, and income against willingness to recapitalize or adopt

electric vehicles, with statistical significance assessed at the 5% level; and (3) Logistic Regression Modeling—binary and ordinal logistic regression models were implemented to estimate the likelihood of drivers' willingness to recapitalize or transition to electric minibuses, with results reported as odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals.

4. Results

The survey captured responses from seven major trotro stations within the Kumasi Metropolitan Area. The highest proportion of respondents (22.67%) were from Kejetia, reflecting its role as the busiest commercial hub and central transport terminal in Kumasi, followed by Anloga Junction (21.41%) and Tech Junction (15.87%). The majority of respondents (41.81%) were between 25–34 years, representing young and active drivers who form the backbone of the sector. Most drivers had attained Senior High School education (58.44%), while 14.61% had Junior High School education. The majority of trotro drivers surveyed were married (74.6%), indicating that most drivers carry family responsibilities.

The majority of drivers (56.4%) operate vehicles on a rental basis, while 24.7% reported being on hire purchase agreements. Only 17.6% of drivers indicated outright ownership of their vehicles. These findings highlight the financial vulnerability of many drivers, as more than three-quarters do not own the vehicles they operate. The majority of respondents (76.3%) reported earning between GHS 200 and 299 per day, while 19.9% earned between GHS 300 and 399. About 80.1% of drivers reported spending GHS 100–199 per day on fuel.

An overwhelming majority of drivers (95%) were aware of modernization or recapitalization discussions, indicating that awareness of reform initiatives is already widespread among drivers. Nearly 8 out of 10 drivers (79%) would definitely be willing to replace their vehicles if provided with support, while 13% expressed conditional willingness. Only 9% were unwilling, suggesting that access to affordable financing or incentive schemes could play a pivotal role in encouraging recapitalization.

Over half of drivers (53%) are very willing to take up a loan with low interest and adequate repayment time, and an additional 12% are willing, showing that about two-thirds of drivers (65%) express strong readiness to recapitalize under favourable loan conditions. A majority of drivers (56%) are very willing to join cooperative arrangements, while another 5% are willing, bringing the total to over 60% supportive of collective schemes.

Access to affordable loans is by far the strongest motivator for drivers to embrace recapitalization. Almost 93% of respondents highly agreed that access to low-interest loans would influence them to replace their vehicles. Tax relief or operational support received strong backing, with about two-thirds (65.5%) highly agreeing. The provision of fixed income guarantees was also highly appealing, with over 62% highly agreeing. Training on the maintenance of modern vehicles generated strong interest, with about 63% highly agreeing.

The high cost of new vehicles is the most significant concern, with about 71% of drivers highly agreeing that replacement vehicles are too expensive. Access to finance also emerged as a central issue, with more than half (55%) of drivers highly agreeing that they would be unable to secure a loan. Another prominent challenge is the availability of spare parts and repairs, with about two-thirds (67%) highly agreeing that sourcing parts would be a difficulty.

Lack of collateral is the single most significant barrier to securing loans, with 84.6% of drivers highly agreeing and a further 10.8% agreeing, bringing total agreement to over 95%. High interest rates were also identified as a major obstacle, with more than half (51.9%) highly agreeing and 37.8% agreeing, representing nearly 90% total agreement.

An overwhelming majority of drivers (78.8%) reported being very willing to switch to electric buses, while an additional 13.1% expressed willingness. Only a small fraction (8.1%) were neutral or hesitant. A significant majority of respondents (66.5%) perceive electric buses as much more expensive than regular trotros. The majority of respondents (73.1%) perceive electricity as being much more expensive than fuel for powering vehicles. However, most drivers anticipate substantial savings on routine servicing and maintenance of electric buses, with 81.6% indicating costs would be much lower.

The high cost of initial purchase (89.4% highly agree) remains the most pressing concern about adopting electric buses. A large share of drivers also feared they would not know how to operate or maintain EVs (76.5% highly agree). Worries about battery lifespan (68.8% agree), long charging times (63.2% agree), and difficulty finding charging stations (55.1% agree) were also reported. The findings indicate that the most influential factor encouraging EV adoption is government subsidy or price reduction (72.5% very important), followed closely by training on how to drive and maintain EVs (70.6%) and union/cooperative support schemes (63.4%).

A chi-square test showed a significant association between daily net income and drivers' willingness to replace their trotro if financial support were provided ($\chi^2(4) = 92.94$, $p < 0.001$). Proportionally, all respondents in the lowest income band (GHS 100–199; 31/31) said they would definitely replace their vehicle if supported. Similarly, the middle-income group (GHS 200–299) expressed strong enthusiasm, with 86% (253/293) stating they would definitely replace. The relationship between income and willingness to invest in a new vehicle using a loan was also highly significant ($\chi^2 = 103.2$, $p < 0.001$). Drivers earning the least (GHS 100–199) were the most enthusiastic, with nearly three-quarters (74%) declaring themselves “very willing” to take up a loan.

Ownership status was used as a proxy for access to financing. The results show a statistically significant relationship between financing access and willingness to recapitalize ($\chi^2(4) = 87.16$, $p < 0.001$). Among hire purchase drivers, 59% stated they would definitely replace their vehicle, while a further 28% said possibly. Vehicle owners also expressed high willingness, with 77% reporting they would definitely recapitalize. Renters formed the largest group ($n = 224$) and showed the strongest enthusiasm: 90% indicated they would definitely recapitalize if given support.

The chi-square test confirmed that the association between age and openness to reform was statistically significant ($\chi^2(12) = 41.5$, $p < 0.001$). While willingness is nearly universal, younger drivers (under 35) were somewhat more likely to select “willing” rather than “very willing,” suggesting a slightly more cautious outlook compared to older cohorts who expressed stronger certainty. A chi-square test confirmed that the relationship between awareness and EV adoption willingness was statistically significant ($\chi^2(3) = 12.6$, $p = 0.006$). Logistic regression further indicated that drivers who were aware of modernization discussions had 2.3 times higher odds of being “very willing” to adopt EVs compared to those who were not (OR = 2.3, $p = 0.014$).

5. Discussion

The findings confirm that financial considerations remain the most decisive factor shaping operator attitudes toward recapitalization. Vehicle cost emerged as the strongest barrier, with almost three-quarters of respondents strongly agreeing that acquiring a new vehicle would be financially burdensome. Access to credit was equally critical, as more than half of the drivers indicated they could not obtain loans to support vehicle replacement, reflecting the structural weaknesses of credit access in Ghana's paratransit industry as noted in earlier studies (Raman & Halm, 1990).

The findings also revealed variations across income and ownership groups. Lower-income drivers were the most enthusiastic about recapitalization, especially through affordable loans, viewing access to

credit as a life-changing opportunity. Middle-income drivers showed similar willingness, though some were more cautious, while higher-income drivers displayed greater reluctance, suggesting alternative investment preferences or concerns about repayment. This challenges the initial hypothesis that higher-income drivers would be more ready to recapitalize. Instead, results suggest that lower-income drivers may be more motivated by access to affordable financing, while higher earners hesitate, perhaps due to repayment concerns or alternative investment priorities.

Ownership status also influenced willingness, with hire-purchase drivers showing stronger inclination to recapitalize compared to outright owners, underscoring the enabling role of financing mechanisms. Renters appeared most eager, seeing recapitalization as a chance to achieve ownership, while hire purchase drivers are also receptive given their existing experience with financing. Owners are supportive but somewhat divided, reflecting more cautious financial attitudes.

Awareness of modernization initiatives was another significant factor. Drivers who were informed about reforms were more than twice as likely to express strong willingness to adopt electric vehicles compared to those unaware. This highlights the role of information and education in shaping perceptions of reform. In addition, drivers placed high importance on job security, tax relief, and training support, confirming that recapitalization is not only about replacing vehicles but also about protecting livelihoods.

Qualitative insights from interviews revealed deep skepticism toward new reforms, with several drivers laughing when electric buses were mentioned, interpreting them as “just another failed promise.” Past failed initiatives, including the Stanbic hire purchase scheme and the West Palm project, were labeled as fraudulent, creating deep distrust. Many respondents expressed frustration with the role of unions, particularly GPRTU, with statements such as “trotro drivers pay and they get nothing” and “GPRTU is only interested in profit” being common.

The results indicate that drivers are highly open to adopting electric buses, provided enabling conditions such as affordability and infrastructure are in place. However, perceptions of high initial purchase costs could pose a major barrier to adoption. The majority of respondents perceive electricity as being much more expensive than fuel, indicating a prevailing misconception or skepticism about the cost advantage of electricity over fuel, which could present a barrier to EV adoption.

6. Policy Implications

The findings suggest that several strategies are essential to ensure successful recapitalization. Affordable financing schemes must be prioritized, with government and financial institutions providing low-interest, long-term credit designed specifically for trotro drivers. Given that lack of collateral is the single most significant barrier, with over 95% of drivers agreeing this prevents them from accessing formal credit, alternative credit assessment mechanisms should be explored. Cooperative guarantees through driver unions could help mitigate risks and expand access.

Incentives such as tax relief, duty reductions, or targeted subsidies should be emphasized, while trade-in programs must be transparent and fair in valuation to overcome existing skepticism. About two-thirds of drivers highly agreed that tax relief would encourage recapitalization, making this a practical and achievable intervention. However, vehicle exchange programs were notably unpopular, with more than half of drivers disagreeing, pointing to either mistrust in trade-in schemes or the perception that such programs would not provide sufficient benefit to drivers.

Awareness creation and training should also be expanded. Demonstration projects, education campaigns, and skills-based training in vehicle maintenance, financial literacy, and digital systems will help drivers gain confidence and adaptability. About 73.8% of drivers highly agreed that hands-on

driving lessons with new vehicles would build their confidence, and 66.2% highly agreed that financial advice on managing loans or payments would be valuable.

Equally important is collaboration with unions such as GPRTU and PROTOA, which can serve as trusted intermediaries and ensure reforms are grounded in the realities of drivers' experiences. However, trust in transport unions is relatively low, with the majority expressing disagreement or neutrality. The government (63.5% highly agree) is the most trusted source of support, followed closely by vehicle companies/dealers and private individuals such as family or friends. Notably, 68.8% of drivers agreed with the statement “I don't trust anyone to help,” underscoring a significant level of distrust within the sector that must be addressed.

For electric vehicle adoption, infrastructure availability is critical. About 74.1% of drivers were very likely to consider switching to electric buses if charging stations were provided near their trotro stations or routes. The government should take the lead in supporting EV adoption, with 83.1% strongly agreeing that subsidies or price reductions are essential. Strong support was also expressed for training (73.0%) and union or cooperative support schemes (68.8%).

Finally, recapitalization should not be treated in isolation but embedded within a broader national transport strategy. Integrating reforms with structured routes, schedules, and technological systems can yield a holistic modernization process while protecting incomes and sustaining livelihoods. The findings indicate strong acceptance of structured operational reforms, with 77.3% of respondents reporting being very willing to adapt to fixed routes and schedules.

7. Conclusion

This study examined the willingness of trotro drivers in Ghana to embrace recapitalization, adopt modern vehicles, and adapt to reforms such as fixed routes and schedules. Using survey evidence from 397 drivers, the research confirmed that financial considerations remain the most decisive factor shaping operator attitudes. Vehicle cost emerged as the strongest barrier, with almost three-quarters of respondents strongly agreeing that acquiring a new vehicle would be financially burdensome.

The findings revealed variations across income and ownership groups. Lower-income drivers were the most enthusiastic about recapitalization, viewing access to credit as a life-changing opportunity. Middle-income drivers showed similar willingness, while higher-income drivers displayed greater reluctance. Awareness of modernization initiatives was another significant factor, with drivers who were informed about reforms being more than twice as likely to express strong willingness to adopt electric vehicles.

Overall, the study shows that drivers are not resistant to modernization itself but are constrained by systemic barriers related to cost, credit, and trust. Willingness is conditional and depends on the practicality, fairness, and financial accessibility of reforms. With the right mix of affordable financing, credible incentives, effective training, and strong union engagement, drivers can become active partners in transport modernization. Such an approach will not only secure their livelihoods but also advance the broader national goals of sustainable urban mobility, environmental protection, and improved passenger services.

The study confirms that Ghana's trotro industry is not inherently resistant to reform but is hampered by systemic challenges. Drivers' willingness to embrace recapitalization and modernization is evident, provided that policies are designed with their financial realities and livelihood concerns at the forefront. The role of drivers as central stakeholders in building a modern, efficient, and sustainable public transport system cannot be overstated. Future transport reforms must recognize that successful

recapitalization depends on integrated financial schemes, targeted driver education, and stakeholder collaboration that safeguard livelihoods while advancing transport modernization.

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